

Reactions and structural studies of 4-(1*H*-benzimidazole-2-yl)-benzonitrile with metal nitrates[†]

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Abstract : One pot synthesis of 4-(1*H*-benzimidazole-2-yl)-benzonitrile (1) under mild reaction conditions and metal-organic hybrid of 4-CN-BIBH with Co^{II} salt have been reported for the first time. In the metal-organic hybrid [Co(NO₃)₂.4H₂O, (4-CN-BIBH)] (3), there is no interaction between the metal and 4-CN-BIBH through dative bonds. 4-CN-BIBH afforded solvated species 4-CN-BIBH. DMSO, (2) in dimethylsulfoxide and reacted with Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Ni^{II} nitrates to form [(4-CN-BIBH₂).NO₃] (4) and M(OH)(NO₃). (H₂O)_{x-1}. Formation of [(4-CN-BIBH₂).NO₃] has been supported by theoretical studies.

Keywords : Synthesis, benzimidazole, structure, solvent co-crystallization, organic-inorganic hybrid, HNO₃ liberation, DFT calculations.

Introduction

Considerable current attention has been paid towards the designing and synthesis of metal organic frameworks because of their intriguing topological networks and potential application as functional materials¹⁻⁹. Main strategy in synthesis of the novel functional materials involves self-assembly processes and employ polydentate organic ligands containing N- and/or O-donor atoms as building blocks¹⁰⁻¹⁵. During past few decades a large number of metal-organic frameworks have been successfully designed and synthesized through judicious choice of the metal ion and ligands. Co-crystallization of two chemical entities is an alternative for storage and transport of the gaseous fuel such as hydrogen or small hydrocarbons¹⁶⁻²⁰. Host networks having cavities are formed by the use of compounds imparting self-binding sites instead of pressurizing or lowering the temperature, where guest molecules can be incorporated. Clathrates with methane are a prominent example^{21,22}. Host-guest systems with layered structure usually have non-specific and non-directional interactions. In this regard, designing and synthesis of the novel coordination ligands are challenging and continuous efforts are being made to tune nature

of the interactions between reactants to obtain desired structures.

Furthermore, enormous current interest has arose in the synthesis of benzimidazole derivatives owing to their involvement in numerous biological processes and wide applications in diverse areas of chemistry²³⁻²⁶, and potential use as anti-viral²⁷⁻²⁹, anti-tumor³⁰ and anti-microbial agents^{31,32}. These also serve as selective neuropeptide YY1 receptor antagonists³³, factor Xa inhibitors³⁴ and smooth muscle cell proliferation inhibitors³⁵. Furthermore, azole derivatives act as ligands in transition metal chemistry^{36,37}. While many coordination compounds containing 2-substituted benzimidazoles have been synthesized and thoroughly studied³⁸ coordination compounds based on 4-substituted benzimidazoles have not yet been reported. We devoted our efforts in this direction and report herein, one pot synthesis of 4-(1*H*-benzimidazole-2-yl)-benzonitrile under rather mild reaction conditions and its anomalous behaviour towards metal nitrates.

Experimental

Materials and method :

Solvents employed in the synthetic procedures were

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of analytical grade. 4-Cyanobenzaldehyde, *o*-phenylenediamine, $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Zn}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Cd}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ were procured from Aldrich and were used as received. HPLC grade solvents were used for all spectroscopic measurements. Infra-red spectra of the compounds were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Nicolet FT-577 spectrophotometer in KBr discs. ^1H NMR spectra were recorded on a JEOL AL-300 FT NMR instrument. UV-Vis spectral studies in the solid state (nujol) and solution (DMSO) were performed on a Shimadzu UV-1700 spectrophotometer.

4-(1*H*-Benzimidazole-2-yl)-benzonitrile (1) : A solution of 4-cyanobenzaldehyde (1.31 g, 10 mmol) in MeOH (10 cm^3) was added to a stirring solution of (1.08 g, 10 mmol) *o*-phenylenediamine in MeOH (25 cm^3) at room temperature. After stirring for 20 min, orange colored compound precipitated, which re-dissolved upon stirring for additional half an hour. The clear solution thus obtained was reduced to half of its volume under reduced pressure and left in refrigerator. Reddish block shaped crystals appeared within 24 h. These were separated, washed with diethyl ether and dried under vacuum. Yield (1.62 g, 74%). Analytical data : Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_9\text{N}_3$: C, 76.71; H, 4.10; N, 19.17. Found : C, 76.64; H, 4.08; N, 19.02%; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3354 (m), 3228 (m), 2216 (s), 1604 (s), 1490 (m), 1373 (w), 1260 (m), 748 (s), 463 (m); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , δ_{H} , ppm) : 9.5 (1H, s, NH), 8.26 (2H, d, bim H), 7.86 (2H, d, CN-BH), 7.58 (2H, d, CN-BH), 7.46 (2H, d, bim H); UV-Vis [solid state; λ_{max} , nm (ϵ , $\text{M}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$)] : 304 (1535), 384 (1778), 473 (1782); UV-Vis [solution; λ_{max} , nm (ϵ , $\text{M}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$)] : 284 (3036), 294 (2079), 429 (2170).

[4-CN-BIBH.DMSO] (2) : Compound **1** (0.219 g, 1 mmol) was dissolved in excess of DMSO (5 cm^3) and left at room temperature for crystallization. White crystals appeared after a week which were separated and dried in air. Yield (0.92 g, 42%). Analytical data : Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_3\text{OS}$: C, 64.64; H, 5.0; N, 10.77. Found : C, 64.52; H, 4.96; N, 10.64%; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3372 (w), 3176 (m), 2235 (m), 1645 (m), 1545 (m), 1440 (s), 1342 (s), 1124 (w), 1043 (m), 979 (w), 846 (m), 749 (s), 670 (w), 567 (m); UV-Vis [solid state; λ_{max} , nm (ϵ , $\text{M}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$)] : 262 (89), 327 (140); UV-Vis [solution; λ_{max} , nm (ϵ , $\text{M}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$)] : 317 (1040), 426 (10).

[Co(NO₃)₂.4H₂O.4-CN-BIBH] (3) : To a solution of 4-CN-BIBH (0.219 mg, 1 mmol) in CH_3CN (8.0 cm^3) a solution of $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (291 mg, 1 mmol) in CH_3CN (5 cm^3) was added with stirring. It gave a pale pink colored solution which was stirred for 30 min. Small amount of brown precipitate separated, which was filtered off. The pink colored filtrate was left for slow evaporation at room temperature. Dark pink block shaped shiny crystals were obtained after two days. These were separated, washed a couple of times with diethyl ether and dried under vacuum. Yield (0.135 g, 62%). Analytical data : Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_5\text{O}_{10}\text{Co}$: C, 35.44; H, 3.50; N, 14.94. Found : C, 35.52; H, 3.50; N, 15.30%; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3416 (m), 3224 (m), 2236 (m), 1624 (s), 1405 (s), 1351 (s), 747 (m), 463 (m); UV-Vis [solid state; λ_{max} , nm (ϵ , $\text{M}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$)] : 262 (1766), 374 (1481); UV-Vis [solution; λ_{max} , nm (ϵ , $\text{M}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$)] : 291 (1781), 427 (1652).

[(4-CN-BIBH)₂.NO₃] (4) : To a solution of 4-CN-BIBH (0.219 g, 1 mmol) in acetonitrile (15 cm^3) a solution of $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.241 g, 1 mmol) in CH_3CN (10 cm^3) was added with stirring. Greenish blue solution thus obtained was further stirred for 1 h. After filtration, resulting light green solution was left for slow evaporation at room temperature. Block shaped diffraction quality crystals were obtained. These were separated washed with diethyl ether and dried under vacuum. Yield (0.153 g, 70%). Analytical data : Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_4\text{O}_3$: C, 59.78; H, 3.50; N, 19.92. Found : C, 59.66; H, 3.46; N, 19.84%; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3413 (w), 3163 (m), 2228 (m), 1631 (m), 1503 (m), 1387 (s), 1315 (s), 856 (m), 758 (s), 614 (m), 551 (m); UV-Vis [solid state; λ_{max} , nm (ϵ , $\text{M}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$)] : 290 (34), 354 (329); UV-Vis [solution; λ_{max} , nm (ϵ , $\text{M}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$)] : 324 (1047), 430 (4).

Reactions of (4-CN-BIBH) with $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Zn}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Cd}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, led to the formation of **4** and $\text{M}(\text{OH})(\text{NO}_3) \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O})_{x-1}$.

Crystallography

Single crystal X-ray data for **1**, **2** and **3** were collected on R-AXIS RAPID II diffractometer and for **4** on a Bruker APEX II area detector at room temperature with Mo-K α radiation ($\lambda = 0.71073 \text{ \AA}$). Structures were solved by direct methods (SHELXS 97) and refined by full-matrix least squares on F^2 (SHELX 97)^{39,40}. All the non-H at-

oms were treated anisotropically. H-atoms attached to the carbon were included as fixed contribution and were geometrically calculated and refined using the SHELX riding model. The crystallographic data for **1-4** are listed in Table 1.

through covalent, coordination or hydrogen bonding interactions. We wished to exploit complexation ability of **1** and carried out its reactions with various metal nitrates. Reactions of **1** with Co(NO₃)₂·6H₂O, Cu(NO₃)₂·3H₂O, Zn(NO₃)₂·6H₂O, Cd(NO₃)₂·4H₂O and Ni(NO₃)₂·6H₂O

Table 1. Crystal and refinement data for **2-4**

Crystal data	2	3	4
<i>M</i> (g mol ⁻¹)	281.34	693.50	282.26
<i>T</i> (K)	100(2)	293(2)	293(2)
Empirical formula	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₃ OS	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ CoN ₅ O ₁₀	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₃
Crystal system	Triclinic	Monoclinic	Monoclinic
Space group	' <i>P</i> -1'	' <i>P</i> 2 ₁ / <i>n</i> '	' <i>P</i> 2 ₁ / <i>n</i> '
<i>a</i> (Å)	7.5351(12)	7.2830(15)	9.2498(13)
<i>b</i> (Å)	10.4729(17)	19.870(4)	26.599(4)
<i>c</i> (Å)	10.7958(17)	11.091(2)	10.6232(14)
α (°)	110.365(2)	90.00	90.00
β (°)	103.446(3)	106.04(3)	94.855(3)
γ (°)	105.405(3)	90.00	90.00
<i>V</i> (Å ³)	718.5(2)	1542.5(5)	2604.3(6)
<i>Z</i>	2	2	5
<i>F</i> (000)	296	714	1225
ρ _{calcd.} (Mg m ⁻³)	1.300	1.493	1.527
μ (mm ⁻¹)	0.159	0.626	1.109
Refln. collected	3696	11910	16947
Parameters refined	216	214	380
GOF on <i>F</i> ²	0.912	1.228	1.056
Final <i>R</i> 1 on observed data	0.0674	0.0583	0.0647
Final <i>wR</i> 2 on observed data	0.1798	0.1507	0.1555

Results and discussion

Synthesis of 4-(1*H*-benzimidazole-2-yl)-benzonitrile is well documented in the literature. It has been synthesized either under harsh reaction conditions or in the presence of a catalyst⁴¹⁻⁵⁶. One pot synthesis of 4-(1*H*-benzimidazole-2-yl)-benzonitrile (**1**) has been achieved in high yield by reaction of *o*-phenylenediamine with 4-cyanobenzaldehyde in methanol in absence of any catalyst under stirring conditions at room temperature. A simple scheme showing the synthesis of **1** and its derivatives is depicted in Scheme 1. Analytical and spectral data of **1** corroborated well with its formulation.

The DMSO solution of **1** afforded co-crystallized species **1**·DMSO **2** held by intermolecular hydrogen bonding interactions. Further it is assumed that due to presence of the donor sites **1** may interact with metal ions

led to some unusual results. Treatment of Co(NO₃)₂·6H₂O with **1** at room temperature in acetonitrile results in the formation organic-inorganic hybrid **1**·[Co(H₂O)₄(NO₃)₂] **3**. On the other hand, upon treatment with Cu(NO₃)₂·3H₂O, Zn(NO₃)₂·6H₂O, Cd(NO₃)₂·4H₂O and Ni(NO₃)₂·6H₂O, it led in the formation of rather unusual species [**1**-H⁺]·[NO₃⁻] **4**, lacking any metal or complex ion and involving strong hydrogen bonding interactions. The resulting species **2**, **3** and **4** have been characterized by various physicochemical techniques and their structures have been determined crystallographically.

Description of the crystal structures

A solution of **1** in DMSO upon slow evaporation afforded white crystals of **1**·[DMSO] **2**^{57,58}. Crystal structure of **2** with atom numbering scheme is depicted in Fig. 1.

Scheme 1

The crystal structure of **2** exhibits an organic-organic hybrid co-crystallized through weak interactions. N(2)-H(2) of **1** and O(1) of DMSO are involved in intermolecular hydrogen bonding. The bond distance is H(2)⋯O(1) is 1.92 Å.

Interaction between **1** and DMSO molecule constructs a square grid motif formed by two DMSO units [Fig. 2 and Fig. S1(a)] along crystallographic-*c*' axis via N-H⋯O hydrogen bonding and C-H⋯π interactions. Fig. S1(b) represents cavity created inside the polyhedra by two DMSO units along crystallographic-*a*' axis. Formation of a cavity by DMSO, where other solvents can be trapped

is quite interesting. The N-H⋯O and C-H⋯π via C(12)⋯H(15B) hydrogen bonding interactions leads to one dimensional chain (Fig. 2, Fig. S2 and Table S1).

Analysis of the crystal structure of **3** (Fig. 3) reveals that there is no interaction between the metal and **1** through dative bonds. Instead, Co^{II} ions form [Co(H₂O)₄(NO₃)₂] via coordination of two nitrate anions and four water molecules and this inorganic moiety is involved in weak bonding interactions with the organic moiety **1** resulting in an inorganic-organic hybrid **1**·[Co(NO₃)₂·4H₂O]. Further, the [Co(H₂O)₄(NO₃)₂] units are held together through intermolecular hydrogen bonding interactions. The Co(1)-

Fig. 1. Crystal structure of **2** with atom numbering scheme.

Fig. S1. A probability of guest incorporation inside the squire grid cavity created by two DMSO molecules in **2** along 'c'-axis. (b) View of **2**, along 'a'-axis. Squire grid cavity created by two DMSO molecule inside the polyhedra.

Fig. S2. Short contact view of **2** showing parallel ribbons.

Fig. 2. Hydrogen bonded view of **2** parallel to the crystallographic-'b' axis. DMSO (space-fill); ligand (capped sticks); red, O; blue, N; yellow, S; gray, C.

Table S1. Matrices for weak interaction of 2-4

2				
D-H...A-X	<i>d</i> D-H [Å]	<i>d</i> H...A [Å]	<i>d</i> D...A [Å]	θ D-H...A [Å]
N(2)-H(2)...O(1)	0.88	1.92	2.797(3)	175
C(4)-H(4)...O(1)	0.95	2.47	3.388(4)	163
C(6)-H(6)...N(3)	0.95	2.59	2.900(4)	100
C(15)-H(15C)...N(3)	0.98(4)	2.49(3)	3.408(4)	157(3)
C(16)-H(16A)...O(1)	1.09(5)	2.38(5)	3.449(4)	166(3)
C(16)-H(16C)...S(1)	1.04(4)	2.86(4)	3.731(3)	142(2)
<i>a</i> = 1-x,-y,-z, <i>b</i> = 2-x,-y,-z, <i>c</i> = x,-1+y,z.				
3				
O1W-H1WA...O3	0.82	1.92	2.7015	158
O1W-H1WB...N4 ^a	0.82	1.84	2.6440	167
O2W-H2WA...N2 ^b	0.82	2.06	2.8609	168
N3-H3A...O2	0.86	2.08	2.8538	150
O2W-H2WB...O2 ^c	0.82	1.97	2.7830	170
C5-H5...N4	0.93	2.59	2.9046	100
<i>a</i> = x,y,1+z, <i>b</i> = 3/2-x,1/2+y,1/2-z, <i>c</i> = -1+x,y,z.				
4				
N(4')-H(4')...O(111)	0.86	1.89	2.750(2)	177
N(5')-H(5')...O(226) ^a	0.86	1.92	2.778(3)	176
N(7')-H(7')...O(113) ^e	0.86	1.95	2.772(2)	160
N(8')-H(8')...O(225) ^f	0.86	1.98	2.758(2)	151
C(4)-H(4)...O(226) ^a	0.93	2.52	3.414(3)	161
C(6)-H(6)...O(111)	0.93	2.38	3.283(3)	164
C(6)-H(6)...N(4')	0.93	2.62	2.936(3)	100
C(12)-H(12)...N(3) ^c	0.93	2.58	3.244(4)	128
C(17)-H(17)...O(111) ^d	0.93	2.58	3.463(3)	159
C(18)-H(18)...O(225) ^b	0.93	2.49	3.262(3)	140
C(20)-H(20)...O(113)	0.93	2.45	3.209(3)	139
C(21)-H(21)...O(226) ^g	0.93	2.46	3.319(3)	154
C(25)-H(25)...O(111)	0.93	2.45	3.229(3)	141
<i>a</i> = 1/2+x,1/2-y,-1/2+z, <i>b</i> = 1+x,y,z, <i>c</i> = -3/2+x,1/2-y,-1/2+z, <i>d</i> = 2-x,-y,1-z, <i>e</i> = x,y,1+z, <i>f</i> = 1-x,-y,1-z, <i>g</i> = 1-x,-y,2-z.				

Fig. 3. Crystal structure of 3 with atom numbering scheme.

O(1)W and Co(1)-O(2)W bond distances are almost equal and 1.999 (3) and 2.049 (4) Å, respectively while, Co(1)-O(1) bond length is 2.194 (3) Å which is comparatively

longer. This authenticates the Jahn-Teller tetragonal elongation about the cobalt center. The coordinated nitrates are *trans*-disposed and metal to nitrate bond distances are elongated⁵⁹⁻⁶². It is in keeping with Co^{II} being a weak field *d*⁷ system, should exhibit Jahn-Teller distortion.

The coordinated nitrate and water molecules are involved in intermolecular hydrogen bonding interactions. The organic and inorganic moieties are held together by strong hydrogen bonding interactions between nitrile group (N2...H2WA-O2W) of 1 and hydrogen from coordinated water molecules. Other hydrogen from the same water molecule is involved in intramolecular hydrogen bonding

with coordinated nitrate oxygen (O2...H2WB-O2W) of another Co^{II} center. Involvement of the cyanide in hydrogen bonding interaction leads to the formation of a linear ladder motif (Fig. 4) through O2-H2WB...N2. Further, a grid network has been resulted from C-H... π interactions (Fig. S3). The interaction distances and angles are well within reported values⁵⁹⁻⁶².

Fig. S3. Grid network of 3 resulting from C-H... π interactions.

Fig. 4. (a) Ladder shaped view of 3, along 'c'-axis (O, red; C, grey; N, sky blue; Co, blue). (b) Ladder topology of 3 (red, frame; blue, steps).

Reaction of 1 with Cu(NO₃)₂·3H₂O under analogous conditions afforded entirely different product 4. Analytical and spectral data 4 corresponded to [1-H⁺][NO₃⁻]. Finally, its structure was authenticated crystallographically^{57,58}. Crystal structure of 4 is depicted in Fig. 5. It is noteworthy that this compound contains 1-H⁺ cations and nitrate anions. The N'(4) atom is protonated to form cation and nitrate anion balances the charge. It has been verified by CBS-Q//B3 calculations. In addition, comparison of the C-N distances suggests that the N(4)'-C(8) and N(5)'-C(8) are almost equal and are 1.342 and 1.340 Å, respectively. These are consistent with the C-N distances in other substituted benzimidazole cations, but different from those of neutral substituted benzimidazole

compounds.

The benzimidazole and cyanophenyl rings are co-planar. Nitrile (C≡N) bond distance is 1.148 Å and is comparable to that in 2/3. The C-N distances in imidazole ring are in the range of 1.340–1.382 Å, shorter than the single bond length of 1.48 Å, but longer than typical C=N distance of 1.28 Å, indicating double bond character^{57,58}. The geometry of nitrate anion is roughly trigonal planar and the N(3) atom deviates by 0.011(2) Å from the plane formed by O(111), O(112) and O(113) atoms. Dihedral angle between the benzimidazole moiety and nitrate plane is 52.30°. Weak interaction studies on 4 (Table S1) revealed that a one dimensional couple cavity is created by intermolecular hydrogen bonding interactions through N(4)-H(4)...O(111). A simple view showing trapping of nitrate between organic moieties is shown in Fig. 6 and Fig. S4. List of hydrogen bond distances is summarized in Table S1.

Fig. 5. Crystal structure of 4 with atom numbering scheme.

Fig. S4. Hydrogen bonding view in **4** along 'a'-axis exhibits trapping of nitrate among ligand molecules.

Most probable mechanism for the formation of **4** may involve removal of HNO_3 from the metal salt $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ employed in the reaction. The formation of $[\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)(\text{OH})] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ by removal of HNO_3 from $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, has been characterized crystallographically^{57,58,63}. Further, proton transfer by protic acids to organic moieties where a hetero atom is present is well documented in the literature⁶⁴⁻⁶⁶. It seems that in the present case liberated HNO_3 acts as donor to 4-CN-BIBH⁶⁴⁻⁶⁶. The protonated 4-CN-BIBH₂ and NO_3^- anions are held together by strong hydrogen bonding interactions. Furthermore, the reactions of $\text{Zn}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Cd}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ with **1**- H^+ under analogous conditions afforded **4** as the major product. It was further confirmed by comparing the cell parameters of the crystals resulting from these reactions. It is assumed that formation of **4** takes place by liberation of HNO_3 from metal nitrate under reaction conditions and HNO_3 thus liberated protonates the organic moiety and NO_3^- ion co-crystallizes with **1** to form **4** and $[\text{M}(\text{NO}_3)(\text{OH})] \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($X = 3, 4$ and **6**). Dissolution in DMSO leads to co-crystallization with neutral **1**.

UV-Vis spectroscopy

Electronic spectra were recorded in the solid state

(nujol). Solid state UV-Vis spectra exhibited three bands at 473 nm, 384 nm and 304 nm for **1**, due to intra-ligand $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions, respectively (Fig. 7). Bands at 473 nm are disappeared in **2**, **3** and **4**. Band appeared at 327 and 262 nm for **2**, 374 and 262 nm for **3** and 354 and 290 nm for **4**. The blue shift in the position of bands in **2**, **3** and **4**, is attributed to the hydrogen bonding, which diminishes electron density on nitrogen of benzi-midazole ring. Consequently weakens to the $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition as well as minimises the extended conjugation. Solution state UV-Vis data are similar to **1** since all the intermolecular weak interactions are broken in solution state.

Fig. 6. Trapping of nitrates between protonated organic molecules in **4**.

Fig. 7. Solid state UV-Vis spectra of 1-4 in nujol.

Table 2. Selected geometrical parameters for 2-4

2		3		4	
C(14)-N'(5)	1.381(3)	C(9)-N(4)	1.382(6)	N(2)-C(9)	1.379(4)
C(23)-N'(8)	1.378(3)	C(10)-N(3)	1.380(6)	N(3)-C(14)	1.383(4)
C(8)-N'(5)	1.339(3)	C(8)-N(4)	1.324(5)	N(2)-C(8)	1.364(4)
C(8)-N'(4)	1.341(3)	C(8)-N(3)	1.360(5)	N(3)-C(8)	1.322(4)
C(1)-N(3)	1.148(4)	C(7)-N(2)	1.132(7)	N(1)-C(1)	1.151(4)
N(1)-O(111)	1.259(2)	Co(1)-O(1)	2.194(3)	S(1)-O(1)	1.514(2)
N(1)-O(112)	1.240(2)	Co(1)-O(2)W	2.049(4)	S(1)-C(15)	1.778(3)
N(1)-O(113)	1.252(2)	Co(1)-O(1)W	1.999(3)	S(1)-C(16)	1.781(3)
		N(1)-O(3)	1.241(5)		
		N(1)-O(2)	1.250(5)		
		N(1)-O(1)	1.252(5)		
		O(1)-H(1)WA	0.8193		
		O(2)-H(2)WA			
C(8)-N'(5)-C(14)	110.4(2)	C(8)-N(4)-C(9)	106.0(4)	C(8)-N(3)-C(14)	104.8(2)
C(8)-N'(4)-C(9)	110.1(2)	C(8)-N(3)-C(10)	107.3(4)	C(8)-N(2)-C(9)	106.6(2)
C(14)-C(9)-N'(4)	106.3(2)	C(9)-C(10)-N(3)	105.7(4)	N(2)-C(9)-C(14)	105.5(2)
C(14)-C(9)-N'(5)	105.7(2)	C(10)-C(9)-N(4)	109.4(4)	N(3)-C(14)-C(9)	110.0(3)
N'(5)-C(8)-N'(4)	107.5(2)	N(3)-C(8)-N(4)	111.7(4)	N(2)-C(8)-N(3)	113.2(2)
N'(4)-C(8)-C(5)	125.3(2)	N(3)-C(8)-C(4)	123.3(4)	N(2)-C(8)-C(5)	122.6(3)
N'(5)-C(8)-C(5)	127.2(2)	N(4)-C(8)-C(4)	125.0(4)	N(3)-C(8)-C(5)	124.2(3)
N'(5)-C(14)-C(13)	132.8(2)	N(4)-C(9)-C(14)	130.1(4)	N(3)-C(14)-C(13)	130.4(3)
N'(4)-C(9)-C(10)	132.3(2)	N(3)-C(10)-C(11)	131.8(4)	N(2)-C(9)-C(10)	131.6(3)
C(6)-C(5)-C(8)	120.4(2)	C(3)-C(4)-C(8)	121.7(4)	C(4)-C(5)-C(8)	121.5(3)

Table-2 (contd.)

C(4)-C(5)-C(8)	121.1(2)	C(5)-C(4)-C(8)	119.3(4)	C(6)-C(5)-C(8)	119.1(3)
C(2)-C(1)-N(3)	178.0(3)	N(2)-C(7)-C(1)	179.8(9)	N(1)-C(1)-C(2)	177.5(3)
O(111)-N(1)-O(112)	120.97(2)	O(1)W-Co(1)-O(2)W	90.7(2)	O(1)-S(1)-C(15)	105.6(1)
O(111)-N(1)-O(113)	17.99(2)	O(1)W-Co(1)-O(1)	90.05(13)	O(1)-S(1)-C(16)	105.8(1)
O(112)-N(1)-O(113)	121.02(2)	O(2)W-Co(1)-O(1)	86.91(16)	C(15)-S(1)-C(16)	99.03(1)
		O(1)-Co(1)-O(1)	180.0		
		O(3)-N(1)-O(1)	121.6(4)		
		HWA-O2W-HWB	121.7		

Conclusions

Through this work we have shown that despite having donor sites 4-(1*H*-benzimidazole-2-yl)-benzonitrile, do not form complexes with the metal ions like Co^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} rather, it leads in the formation of organic-inorganic hybrids (**3** and **4**) and organic-organic **2**. It strongly shows that in this particular case weak interactions are preferred over complexation.

Supplemental material

CIF files contain X-ray crystallographic data for compounds **1-3** (CCDC-734080 (**2**), 710502 (**3**), 710503 (**4**) and some figures of compounds **1-3** are given. Matrices for various intra and inter-molecular interactions in **2-4**.

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